

Original Research Report

Proximate Composition, Functional Properties and Sensory attributes of Gruels prepared from Blends of Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flours

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Abstract: This study was carried out to evaluate the proximate composition and functional properties of sorghum and pigeon pea composite flours and the sensory properties of gruel prepared from the blends. Flours were produced from sorghum and pigeon pea seeds. The composite flours of sorghum and pigeon pea were blended using different proportions designated as SGF, PPF, SP1, SP2, SP3, SP4 and SP5. The proximate composition, functional and sensory properties of the blends were determined using standard methods. Proximate result showed significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in protein (11.25 – 23.10%), crude fibre (3.05- 7.35%) and ash (2.01 – 4.72%) and significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in fat (4.53 - 1.80%) and carbohydrate (72.06 – 55.88%) with increase in percent pigeon pea flour in the blends. There were significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in the energy value of the blends. The functional properties result showed that bulk density, water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity, wettability, gelation capacity and swelling index ranged from 0.610 – 0.681g/ml, 1.33 – 2.25g/g, 1.28 – 1.73g/g, 80.06 – 165.12s, 9.11-10.0% and 1.56 – 2.54 respectively. The sensory result showed that the gruels made from the blends were acceptable to the panelists. The blends can be useful as good weaning foods for children.

Keywords: Composite Flour, Gruel, Pigeon Pea, Sorghum, Weaning Foods

1. Introduction

The powder made from grinding dry foods such as cereals, beans, roots, and tubers, is known as flour. Composite flours are a combination of many types of flour made from roots, tubers, cereals, and legumes, with or without wheat flour (Awolu et al., 2016). Composite flours are produced from locally sourced ingredients to use in place of wheat flour for baking bread and other baked items (Arukwe et al., 2021) and complementary foods. The economy of emerging nations is being harmed by the importation of wheat, and food security is at risk. Therefore, using composite flour to make baked goods, breakfast cereals, weaning foods, and other products will be good for developing nations like Nigeria's economy because it will cut down on the cost of importing wheat flour, increase local crop production, and give farmers more money and jobs while also making their products more affordable. Many people in Africa obtain their dietary patterns largely from cereals and legumes, which are also their primary sources of proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. Legume proteins are frequently used in food compositions to replace protein in cereals due to their chemical and nutritional qualities (Okoye & Mazi, 2011).

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) serves as a staple food for many, especially the poor people in Africa (Kinyua et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2019). The majority of its production and consumption occurs in nations including the United States, China, India, Nigeria, Mexico, Argentina, Sudan, and Egypt. It is recognized as the fifth most significant grain in the world, after wheat, maize, rice, and barley (Dicko et al., 2006). In Nigeria, it is mostly cultivated in the Northern part. It serves as source of energy, protein (but of low quality), vitamins and minerals. According to Sodipo and Fashakin (2011), grains are high in the sulphur-containing amino acids methionine and cysteine but low in lysine and tryptophan, whereas legumes are high in lysine and tryptophan but low in methionine and cysteine. Therefore, adding legumes like pigeon pea can improve the protein content of sorghum. Sorghum is used to make a wide range of dishes, including porridge, bread, and baby food.

The pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* L.), grown mostly as a subsistence crop in Africa's tropical and subtropical regions, is ranked as the sixth most significant edible legume in the world (ICRISAT, 2008). Pigeon pea can be used as a supplement to sorghum to increase its nutritional value since it is high in protein, important amino acids, notably lysine, minerals, fibre, and vitamins (Kaushal et al., 2012). On the other hand, sorghum and pigeon pea contain anti-nutrients. Soaking, boiling, and sprouting have all been used to increase the nutritious value of grains. One of the processing procedures that increase the nutritional characteristics of grains and legumes by lowering anti-nutrients is boiling. The need to add legume flour to gruel was motivated by the high prevalence of protein deficiency in Nigeria and other poor nations, particularly among children who are weaning. Traditional weaning diets include cereal porridge (gruel), which is typically cooked with locally accessible grains such as maize, sorghum, or millet. However, they do not provide enough nutrients, especially protein, for infants. To boost the nutritional value of the products produced from the blends, pigeon pea flour can be used in addition to sorghum flour. Pigeon pea flour, which is high in protein, has the potential to raise the protein content of sorghum-pigeon pea flour blends, hence raising the protein content of the gruels generated from them and boosting the protein intake of consumers. Pigeon peas are an underused legume, and using them as a complement to sorghum flour to make sorghum-pigeon pea weaning meals will increase the use of this crop for commercial reasons, boosting its value and cultivation. The purpose of this study was to make sorghum and pigeon pea seed flours, mix them and assess their proximate composition and functional qualities, and assess the sensory qualities of gruels made from the blends.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Due to the issue of widespread protein malnutrition among children in Nigeria and other developing nations brought on by insufficient intake of protein-rich meals, attempts have been made to use underutilized leguminous seeds like pigeon pea to supplement the traditional cereal-based diets. Children's protein intake will be improved and protein deficiency will be prevented by weaning them onto diets made from sorghum and pigeon pea flour mixtures. The manufacture of sorghum-pigeon pea weaning meals might be improved by adding pigeon pea as a supplement to sorghum flour. This would increase the crop's cultivation and improve its commercial application.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study was to produce flours from sorghum and pigeon pea and evaluate the proximate composition, functional properties and sensory attributes of gruels prepared from the blends. The specific objectives are to:

- (a) Produce flours from sorghum and pigeon pea grains.
- (b) Blend the flours of sorghum and pigeon pea and determine their proximate composition and functional properties.
- (c) Prepare gruels from the blends and determine their sensory properties.

1.3. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- (a) What are the proximate compositions of blends of sorghum and pigeon pea flour?
- (b) What are the functional properties of blends of sorghum and pigeon pea flour?
- (c) What are the sensory/overall acceptability of gruels prepared from blends of sorghum and pigeon pea flour?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The design employed for this study was the experimental design. The experimental design was completely randomized design since the experimental units are homogenous and controlled.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The research was carried out with informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents who voluntarily participated in the sensory evaluation of the study. The standard methods for sensory evaluation studies were strictly adhered to. The ethical demands of sensory evaluation as required in research studies were strictly complied with.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was carried out in the Food Processing laboratory of the Department of Food Science and Technology, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.

2.3. Raw Materials Procurement

Sorghum grains and pigeon pea seeds were procured from Ubani Main Market in Umuahia North Local Government Area, Abia State.

2.4. Sample Preparation

Sorghum and pigeon pea seeds totaling two kilogrammes (kg) each underwent sorting, cleaning, and water washing before being rinsed and drained. The seeds were submerged in water for around

12 hours (with periodic water changes) the water was emptied.

2.4.1. Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flour Production

With minor modifications, the process described by Arukwe et al. (2017) was applied to produce boiling sorghum flour and boiled pigeon pea flour. Sorghum flour was made by boiling soaked sorghum grains in water for 1 hour at 100°C. The water was drained, and the grains were dried in a 60°C oven for 7 hours (Gallenkemp, 300 Plus, England). Disc attrition mill (Asiko A11, Addis Nigeria), conventional sieve (1.0 mm mesh size), and polyethylene packs were used to turn dry grains into flour. To prepare pigeon pea flour, the soaked pigeon pea grains were manually dehulled and boiled for an hour at 100°C in water. After the water was drained, the grains were dried in an oven at 60°C for seven hours (Gallenkemp, 300 Plus, England). Disc attrition mill (Asiko A11, Addis Nigeria), conventional sieve (1.0 mm mesh size), and polyethylene packs were used to turn dry grains into flour.

2.4.2. Formulation of Composite Flours

As indicated in Table 1, sorghum and pigeon pea seed flours were combined in a variety of ratios and classified as SGF, PPF, SP1, SP2, SP3, SP4, and SP5. The blending was carried out to find the sample that customers would find more nourishing and preferable.

Table 1: Formulation of sorghum and pigeon pea composite flours

Sample	Sorghum flour	Pigeon pea flour	Total
SGF	100	0	100
PPF	0	100	100
SPF1	90	10	100
SPF2	80	20	100
SPF3	70	30	100
SPF4	60	40	100
SPF5	50	50	100

Key: SGF = 100% sorghum flour, PPF = 100% pigeon pea flour, SP1 = 90% sorghum and 10% pigeon pea flour, SP2 = 80% sorghum flour and 20% pigeon pea flour, SP3 = 70% sorghum flour and 30% pigeon pea flour, SP4 = 60% sorghum flour and 40% pigeon pea flour and SP5 = 50% sorghum flour and 50% pigeon pea flour.

2.4.3. Preparation of Gruels from blends of Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flours

Each sample (100g) was homogeneously combined with 200ml of water to create a slurry, which was then allowed to stand for 5m to ensure appropriate water absorption. A saucepan was filled with around 300ml of water and brought to a boil. The slurry was then gradually added while being constantly stirred to prevent lump formation until a thin paste was formed (gruel). Each sample has ten grammes of granulated sugar added for flavour. The samples of gruels were then utilized for sensory assessment.

2.5. Proximate Analysis and Energy Value Determination

2.5.1. Determination of Moisture Content

The AOAC (2010) method was used to determine the moisture content of the samples. Each sample was weighed into a separate moisture container with two grammes. They were then placed in a 150°C oven for 3 hours, with drying stopping when two consecutive results varied by 0.001. After chilling in a desiccator, the samples were weighed. The moisture content of the samples was then calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100$$

where: W_1 = initial weight of empty can.

W_2 = weight of empty can + sample before drying.

W_3 = final weight of empty can + sample after drying.

2.5.2. Determination of Ash Content

Using the method recommended by AOAC (2010), the samples' ash content was determined. The ceramic crucible was desiccated-dried and cooled before being weighed. A crucible was filled with two grammes of each sample, and the weight was noted. The samples were placed in the crucible and heated in the muffle furnace to 550°C . For a period of three hours, this temperature was maintained. After that, the muffle furnace was allowed to cool before the crucibles were taken out, cooled, and weighed. The following formula was used to compute the ash content:

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Where: W_2 = weight of crucible + ash,

W_1 = weight of empty crucible.

2.5.3. Fat Content Determination

According to the AOAC (2010), instructions, solvent extraction in a soxhlet device was used to assess the samples' fat content. Each sample was placed in a soxhlet reflux flask linked to an upper condenser, a weighted oil extraction flask, and a flask containing 200ml of petroleum ether after being wrapped in filter paper. The materials for extraction were completely submerged in the reflux flask when the ether boiled. Syphons transferred the oil extract back to the bubbling solvent in the reflux flask once it was full. The procedure of boiling, condensation, and reflux was allowed to continue for four hours before the defatted samples were removed. Before weighing, the oil extract in the flux was dried in an oven at 60 degrees Celsius for thirty minutes

$$\% \text{ Fat} = \frac{\text{Weight of fat}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.5.4. Crude Fibre determination

The samples' crude fibre content was assessed using the AOAC (2010) methodology. Two grammes of each sample were boiled at reflux for 30 minutes in a 200ml solution that contained 1.25 g of tetraoxosulphate (vi) acid (H_2SO_4) for every 100ml of solution. A flauted funnel was used to filter the solution through linen, which was then washed in water to remove any remaining acidity. In a beaker with 100ml of the solution, the residue was then placed and cooked for 30 minutes. In a Gosh crucible, the residual residue was passed through a thin yet dense pad of cleaned and burned asbestos. In an electric oven, the residue was then dried and weighed. After being burned, cooled, and weighed, the waste. The crude fibre content of the sample was then estimated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Crude fibre} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_1}$$

Where: W_1 = weight of sample used, W_2 = weight of crucible plus sample,

W_3 = weight of sample crucible

2.5.5. Determination of Crude Protein

The Kjeldahl technique, as described by the AOAC (2010), was used to assess the samples' crude protein content. The digestion flask was filled with one gramme of the material. The sample was

supplemented with Kjeldahl catalyst (tablets of selenium). After adding 20 millilitres of concentrated sulfuric acid to the sample and fastening it to the digester for eight hours, a clear solution was created. The AOAC (2010), Kjeldahl technique was used to determine the crude protein of the samples. In the digestion flask, one gramme of the material was placed. The sample was treated with Kjeldahl catalyst (Selenium tablets). The material was treated with 20 millilitres of strong sulphuric acid, and after being secured to the digester for eight hours, a clear solution was produced. The total percentage of protein was calculated:

% protein = % nitrogen x conversion factor (6.25).

2.5.6. Determination of Carbohydrate Content

Using the AOAC (2010) described formula, the samples' carbohydrate content was determined.

% carbohydrate = 100 - % (protein + fat + fibre + ash + moisture content).

2.5.7. Determination of Energy Value

AOAC (2010) recommended Atwater factors were used to assess the energy value.

The energy value was calculated by multiplying the proportion of protein, fat and carbohydrate by their respective physiological fuel value of 4, 9, and 4 kcal/g respectively and taking the sum of their products.

The energy value was determined as follows:

$F_e = (\% \text{ CP} \times 4) + (\% \text{ CF} \times 9) + (\% \text{ CHO} \times 4)$

Where: F_e = Food energy (in grain calories), CP= Crude protein

CF= Crude fat, CHO= Carbohydrate

2.6. Determination of Functional Properties

2.6.1. Determination of Water Absorption Capacity

Water absorption capacity was measured according to Onwuka (2018) description. A conical graduated centrifuge tube was filled with one (1g) of the sample, which was weighed first. The sample was well mixed with a Waring whirl mixer, 10ml was added, and the sample was left at room temperature for 30 m before being centrifuged at 5000g for 30m. A 10 ml measuring cylinder was used to determine the amount of free water (supernatant). The amount of water absorbed was calculated as follows: total water minus free water x 1g/ml.

2.6.2. Determination of Oil Absorption Capacity (OAC)

For the determination of OAC, the Onwuka (2018) technique was used. The oil utilized was refined soybean oil having a density of 0.92g/ml. For 30 seconds, one (1) gramme of the sample was combined with 10ml of the oil (V_1). The sample was centrifuged for 30minutes at 10,000rpm using a Centrion Scientific Model K241 after 30 minutes at room temperature. A 10ml cylinder was used to determine the quantity of oil separated as supernatant (V_2). The volume difference was calculated as the amount of oil absorbed by the samples. The following equation was used to compute the obtained result:

$$\text{Oil absorption capacity} = \frac{(V_1 - V_2)P}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Where, V_1 = the initial volume of oil used, V_2 = the volume not absorbed

P = the density of oil (0.92 g/ml)

2.6.3. Determination of Bulk Density

The sample was carefully poured into a graduated measuring cylinder with a 10ml capacity after the cylinder had been weighed. After filling to the 10 ml mark, the cylinder's bottom was gently tapped several times on the lab bench to ensure that the sample level was not diminished. According

to Onwuka (2018), the formula for calculating bulk density (g/ml) was weight of sample (g)/volume of sample (ml).

2.6.4. Determination of Wettability

The wettability of the flour samples was tested utilizing the Onwuka (2018) method. One (1) gramme of each flour sample was weighed out and put into a 25ml graduated measuring cylinder with a 1cm diameter using an analytical balance. The finger was then inverted, clamped at a height of 10cm over the surface of a 600ml beaker containing 500ml of distilled water, and placed over the open end of the cylinder in each case. Once the finger was taken off, the test sample was then allowed to discharge. The wettability was determined by the time required for the sample to become fully saturated.

2.6.5. Determination of Gelatinization Temperature

A beaker containing one gramme (1g) of sample was filled with 10 ml of distilled water, which was then agitated in order to create a homogeneous mixture. The sample was heated and continually whirled in a beaker filled with boiling water until it gelled. A thermometer was used to measure the temperature 30 seconds after gelation (Onwuka, 2018).

2.6.6. Determination of Swelling Index

This is the ratio of the expanded volume of a unit weight of flour to its initial volume. We followed the steps Onwuka (2018) had outlined One (1) grammes of the flour sample were weighed out into a pristine, dry measuring cylinder. After measuring the sample's height (beginning height), 5cm of distilled water was added. Having been allowed to stand for an hour without being disturbed, this was observed and captured once more (final height). After then, the swelling index was calculated by dividing the final height by the starting height.

2.7. Sensory Evaluation of Gruels from Blends of Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flours

Using the 9-point Hedonic scale (where 9 is very much liked and 1 is very much disliked), as defined by Iwe (2014), sensory evaluation of the gruel samples generated from blends of sorghum and pigeon pea flours was conducted, with Nutrend (Nestle Foods) serving as the control. The evaluation of appearance, taste, texture, flavour, and general acceptance was carried out by a panel of twenty semi-trained participants.

2.8. Data Analysis Technique

Using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0, the data was subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA), and treatment means were separated using Duncan's multiple range testing at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Proximate Composition and Energy Value of Flour Mixtures from Sorghum and Pigeon Pea.

The Proximate Composition and Energy Value of Flour Mixtures from Sorghum and Pigeon Pea shown in Table 2. Moisture levels in the samples did not alter substantially ($p > 0.05$). Low moisture content was found in the composite flours, which varied from 7.12% to 7.16%. Since spoilage bacteria will not flourish at such low moisture and moisture-dependent biochemical processes will be reduced, this is beneficial for the flours' long shelf life (Onimawo & Akubor, 2012). All of the blends' moisture contents fall within the range of 7%, which is the Recommended Dietary Allowance for foods (FAO/WHO, 1998). The protein content of the sorghum and pigeon pea composite flours differed significantly ($p < 0.05$). Samples SGF and PPF had the lowest and highest protein contents of the blends, respectively, ranging from 11.25 to 23.10%. With a percent increase in

pigeon pea flour, the protein content significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) for the other samples. As pigeon pea flour has a lot of protein, this is to be expected (Kaushal et al., 2012) and this justifies the desire for supplementation of sorghum flour with pigeon pea flour. The composite blends will provide the required dietary protein for children and adults. Nwanekezi et al. (2017) observed similar findings. The RDA for protein in meals is larger than 6.0mg/100g (FAO/WHO, 1998), and the protein value found for the mix SP5 is within this range, however the control, sample PPF is greater (23.10%) than the RDA.

Table 2: Sorghum and pigeon pea flour blends proximate composition and energy value

Sample	Moisture %	Protein %	Crude Fibre %	Ash %	Fat %	Carbohydrate %	Energy Kcal
SGF	7.13 ^a +0.00	11.25 ^g +0.02	3.05 ^g +0.01	2.01 ^g +0.10	4.53 ^a +0.02	72.06 ^a +0.01	374.01 ^a +0.01
PPF	7.15 ^a +0.02	23.10 ^a +0.00	7.35 ^a +0.02	4.72 ^a +0.01	1.80 ^g +0.01	55.88 ^f +0.00	332.12 ^g +0.04
SP1	7.16 ^a +0.01	12.15 ^f +0.01	3.58 ^f +0.00	2.20 ^f +0.00	4.15 ^b +0.10	70.74 ^e +0.00	368.91 ^b +0.00
SP2	7.15 ^a +0.02	13.50 ^e +0.00	3.96 ^e +0.10	2.42 ^e +0.00	4.00 ^c +0.00	68.97 ^d +0.01	365.88 ^c +0.02
SP3	7.12 ^a +0.00	14.20 ^d +0.02	4.66 ^d +0.00	2.74 ^d +0.01	3.85 ^d +0.00	67.43 ^c +0.00	361.17 ^d +0.01
SP4	7.15 ^a +0.01	15.35 ^c +0.01	4.85 ^c +0.04	2.98 ^c +0.02	3.70 ^e +0.01	66.02 ^b +0.02	358.78 ^c +0.00
SP5	7.12 ^a +0.02	16.50 ^b +0.00	5.15 ^b +0.10	3.05 ^b +0.00	3.55 ^f +0.00	64.63 ^b +0.01	356.47 ^f +0.10

* The means along the column with the same superscripts do not differ substantially ($p < 0.05$).

Key: SGF = 100% sorghum flour, PPF = 100% pigeon pea flour, SP1 = 90% sorghum and 10% pigeon pea flour, SP2 = 80% sorghum flour and 20% pigeon pea flour, SP3 = 70% sorghum flour and 30% pigeon pea flour, SP4 = 60% sorghum flour and 40% pigeon pea flour and SP5 = 50% sorghum flour and 50% pigeon pea flour.

The samples' crude fibre contents varied from 3.05% to 7.35%, with samples SGF and PPF registering the lowest and highest values, respectively. The crude fibre content of the blends varied significantly ($p < 0.05$). The percentage of pigeon pea flour in the blends rose along with the rise in crude fibre. This is consistent with the findings of Nwanekezi et al. (2017), who discovered that pigeon pea flour has a significant amount of crude fibre. Crude fibre, which comprises cellulose, hemicelluloses, pectin, lignins, and other plant components, is the indigestible portion of plant matter (Ogundele, et al., 2015). This suggest that using up of foods prepared with these flours will help to lower serum cholesterol, obesity and maintain the healthy condition of the intestines (Ameh et al., 2013). According to the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) of 4.0 mg/100g for crude fibre in foods (FAO/WHO, 1998), all of the blends' crude fibre contents are in compliance with the RDA for infants.

Sorghum and pigeon pea composite flours have remarkably different ash contents ($p < 0.05$). The range of the blends' ash concentrations was 2.01 to 4.72%, with the samples SGF and PPF having the lowest and highest amounts, respectively. The ash content of the blends increased as the amount of pigeon pea flour increased. As a result, pigeon pea flour contains more ash than sorghum flour. A food's ash content reveals its mineral content (Sanni et al., 2008). The assertion that pigeon pea is a rich source of minerals is supported by the spike in ash that occurs when the amount of pigeon pea flour is increased (Nwanekezi et al., 2017). The flour blends are more likely to include essential minerals needed for body growth, bone health, and metabolic process (Ikpeama et al., 2014). All of the blends' ash contents fall below the range of the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) of 5.0 mg/100g (FAO/WHO, 1998) for ash content in foods. The fat percentage of the sorghum and pigeon

pea composite flours varied from 1.80 to 4.53%, and there were notable differences ($p < 0.05$). The fat level reduced as the percentage of pigeon pea flour increased. Pigeon pea flour has a low fat level, according to Nwanekezi et al. (2017). The low fat content will contribute to the low calorie content of the flour samples as well as lengthening the shelf life of the blends by decreasing the likelihood of rancidity. The blends are suitable as raw materials for the creation of healthy food products for the elderly due to their low fat content. The recommended daily allowance (RDA) for fat in meals is $> 2.0 \text{ mg}/100\text{g}$ (FAO/WHO, 1998), and the fat levels of the blends are within this range with the exception of the control, sample PPF, where the fat component is low than (1.80%). Dietary fat increases the palatability of food, transports fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, & K), and provides energy (Makinde & Oladipo, 2012).

The carbohydrate content of the samples ranged between 55.88% and 72.06%. Significant variations in the blends' carbohydrate content ($p < 0.05$) were found. Sample SGF recorded the highest value while sample PPF had the least value. Given that, sorghum is a cereal and that cereals are a high source of carbohydrates, this is to be anticipated. As the percentage of pigeon pea flour increased, the blends' carbohydrate content decreased. This implies that the flour blends will be helpful for making dishes for diabetes people who need low-carb diets. All of the blends' carbohydrate contents are over the recommended daily allowance (RDA) of $> 60\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ (FAO/WHO, 1998) for carbohydrates in foods.

The energy values of the sorghum and pigeon pea combination varied from 332.12 to 374.01 kcal, and there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Sample SGF recorded the highest value while sample PPF had the lowest value. With an increase in pigeon pea flour percentage, the energy value fell. This might be due to pigeon pea flour's low carbohydrate and fat content. According to this, composite blends with lower energy values can serve as functional meals and are appropriate for those who are overweight, obese, diabetic, have high blood pressure. Energy is a crucial component of food and is needed for every human function. The greatest energy value found in sorghum flour can be ascribed to the sample's greater carbohydrate content. This is consistent with the study of Khan et al. (2013), which found that carbs constitute a crucial and primary source of energy. The caloric content found in this study is rather greater than the 200kcal for infants aged 6 to 8 months and 300kcal for infants aged 9 to 11 months that is advised for infants in underdeveloped nations. However, the values for energy are lower than 500kcal per day for 12 - 23 months of age (FAO/WHO, 1998).

3.2. Functional Properties of the Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flour Blends

The criteria that influence how and where food items are used might be referred to as their functional qualities (Adeleke & Odedeji, 2010). Table 3 displays the functional parameters of the sorghum and pigeon pea flour blends. There were considerable differences ($p < 0.05$) in the bulk densities of the composite flours which ranged from 0.610 - 0.681g/ml. Sample SGF had the highest value while the least value was recorded for sample PPF. The bulk densities of the blends decreased as the percentage of pigeon pea flour increased. The reduction in bulk density corroborates the work of Arukwe et al. (2021). In the food sector, bulk density is crucial for evaluating packaging needs, material handling, and application (Falade & Okafor, 2015). Different associated elements, such as the strength of the attractive interparticle interactions, the size of the particles, and the number of contact sites, might be to blame for the variance in bulk density of the wheat samples (Chandra et al., 2015). The blends' low bulk densities suggest that the flours will need more packing space since the

smaller the mass, the bigger the space required. Since low bulk density meals are necessary for infants to enable them to swallow it easily without choking or suffocating, the flours can be utilized to formulate baby food (Ikujenlola et al., 2013). The low bulk density flours can also be used to produce foods with less retro-gradation (Chukwu et al., 2018).

The samples' ability to absorb water ranged from 1.33 to 2.25g/g. Sample PPF had the lowest value, whereas sample SGF had the highest. Except for samples SGF and SP1, where there was no major difference ($p>0.05$), all of the samples' water absorption capacity values showed significant differences ($p<0.05$). As the percentage of pigeon pea flour increased, the ability to absorb water decreased. Since a decrease in carbohydrate content has been shown to reduce the capacity of flours to absorb water, this can be linked to the high protein and low carbohydrate concentration of pigeon pea flour (Nwanekezi et al., 2019). Therefore, the composite blends with low water absorption power values will have long storability because; the maximum amount of water that food can absorb and retain is indicated by its water absorption capacity.

Table 3: Sorghum and Pigeon pea flour mixture functional properties

Sample	Bulk Density (g/ml)	Water Absorption Capacity(g/g)	Oil Absorption Capacity(g/g)	Wettability (s)	Gelation Capacity (%)	Swelling Index
SGF	0.681 ^a +0.00	2.25 ^a +0.02	1.28 ^g +0.02	80.06 ^g +0.10	10.02 ^a +0.02	1.56 ^g +0.01
PPF	0.610 ^g +0.01	1.82 ^c +0.00	1.73 ^a +0.00	165.12 ^a +0.01	9.25 ^e +0.00	2.54 ^a +0.00
SP1	0.670 ^b +0.02	2.21 ^a +0.02	1.33 ^f +0.01	84.80 ^f +0.00	10.00 ^a +0.02	1.71 ^b +0.02
SP2	0.661 ^c +0.01	2.00 ^b +0.01	1.38 ^e +0.00	90.53 ^e +0.00	9.75 ^b +0.00	1.88 ^c +0.00
SP3	0.648 ^d +0.00	1.78 ^d +0.02	1.45 ^d +0.10	100.01 ^d +0.01	9.72 ^b +0.01	2.05 ^d +0.00
SP4	0.636 ^e +0.01	1.55 ^e +0.00	1.50 ^c +0.00	108.22 ^c +0.02	9.58 ^c +0.00	2.22 ^e +0.02
SP5	0.625 ^f +0.00	1.33 ^f +0.01	1.56 ^b +0.10	117.30 ^b +0.00	9.50 ^d +0.01	2.30 ^f +0.01

* The means along the column with the same superscripts do not differ substantially ($p<0.05$).

Key: SGF = 100% sorghum flour, PPF = 100% pigeon pea flour, SP1 = 90% sorghum and 10% pigeon pea flour, SP2 = 80% sorghum flour and 20% pigeon pea flour, SP3 = 70% sorghum flour and 30% pigeon pea flour, SP4 = 60% sorghum flour and 40% pigeon pea flour and SP5 = 50% sorghum flour and 50% pigeon pea flour.

The oil absorption capacity of the samples ranged between 1.28g/g and 1.73g/g. The oil absorption capacity of the samples recorded significant differences ($p<0.05$) with sample SGF having the least value and sample PPF had the highest value. The values for oil absorption capacity increased for the composite blends with increase in percent pigeon pea flour. Protein's ability to bind fat is shown by its oil absorption capability. It is significant because fats function as flavour retainers and boost the mouth feel of meals (Otegbayo et al., 2013). This indicates that the blends with high oil absorption capacity will improve mouth-feel and flavor retention (Peter et al., 2017) and also extend shelf life of bakery or meat products, and soup mixes where fat absorption is desired (Chandra et al., 2015).

There were significant differences in the wettability of the composite flour samples which ranges from 80.06 – 165.12s. Sample SGF had the least value while sample PPF had the highest value. The values for wettability increased for the blends with increase in percent pigeon pea flour. This implies that the flour samples will disperse slower in water than the samples with low wettability. The high wettability of pigeon pea flour could be attributed to its high fibre content. The polarity of the flour particles and the surface tension of liquid play a major role in the wettability of

flours (Onimawo & Akubor, 2012).

Sorghum and pigeon pea composite flours had a gelation capability that ranged from 9.25% to 10.02%. Sample PPF had the lowest value, whereas sample SGF had the highest value, which was not significantly different from sample SP1 ($p > 0.05$). Several of the samples' gelation capacities varied considerably ($p < 0.05$). As the proportion of pigeon pea flour rose, the samples' capacity to gel decreased. The findings by Arukwe et al. (2017) concur that this might be attributable to the high protein component of pigeon pea flour. Gelation capacity is a food material's ability to form gel, and that is significant component influencing food texture. Gelation capacity indicates the concentration of flour needed to form gel during food preparation (Msheliza et al., 2018).

The samples' swelling indices, which ranged from 1.56 to 2.54, displayed appreciable differences ($p < 0.05$). Sample PPF had the greatest value, whereas sample SGF had the lowest value. As the percentage of pigeon pea flour grew, so did the blends' swelling index. The swelling index of flours, which also reflects the strength of the association forces inside the granules, indicates the degree of crystalline packing of the starch granules (Amiri et al., 2009). This suggests that an array of commodities be capable of be prepared using composite flours with high swelling indices.

3.3. Sensory Properties of Gruels Prepared from Sorghum and Pigeon Pea Flour combination

Table 4 displays the sensory results of the gruels produced from a combination of sorghum and pigeon pea flours and Nutrend cereal (control). The sensory qualities of appearance, taste, texture, flavour, and general acceptability varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) between the samples and the control (Nutrend). For appearance, the sensory score varied from 5.6 to 7.5. Among the test samples, Sample 70:30 (70 percent sorghum and 30 percent pigeon pea flour) was the most favoured. The control sample (Nutrend) was the most favoured in terms of flavour, followed by samples 70:30 and 75:25, all of which differed considerably from the others. All of the parameters analyzed showed a preference for the control sample (Nutrend). This could be explained by the panellists' familiarity with Nutrend as it is a widely available product. Even though all of the test samples were satisfactory based on the sensory scores, 70:30 was favoured among them in all criteria examined. The sensory evaluations increased as the test samples' pigeon pea flour content increased. This could be a result of the blends' enhanced texture (Mouth feel).

Table 4: Sensory Characteristics of Sorghum and Blends of Pigeon Pea Flour Gruels

Samples	Appearance	Taste	Texture	Flavour	Overall acceptability
SGF	5.6 ^f +0.0	6.0 ^g +0.0	5.8 ^g +0.0	6.0 ^f +0.0	5.8 ^g +0.0
PPF	5.7 ^e +0.0	6.1 ^f +0.0	6.0 ^f +0.0	6.0 ^f +0.0	6.0 ^f +0.0
SP1	6.0 ^d +0.0	6.2 ^e +0.0	6.2 ^e +0.0	6.1 ^e +0.0	6.1 ^e +0.0
SP2	6.0 ^d +0.0	6.3 ^d +0.0	6.2 ^e +0.0	6.2 ^d +0.0	6.2 ^d +0.0
SP3	6.1 ^c +0.0	6.3 ^d +0.0	6.4 ^d +0.0	6.2 ^d +0.0	6.2 ^d +0.0
SP4	6.5 ^b +0.0	6.5 ^c +0.0	6.5 ^c +0.0	6.4 ^c +0.0	6.5 ^c +0.0
SP5	6.5 ^b +0.0	6.6 ^b +0.0	6.7 ^b +0.0	6.5 ^b +0.0	6.6 ^b +0.0
Nutrend	7.5 ^a +0.0	7.7 ^a +0.0	7.7 ^a +0.0	7.8 ^a +0.0	7.8 ^a +0.0

* The means along the column with the same superscripts do not differ substantially ($p < 0.05$).

Key: SGF = 100% sorghum flour, PPF = 100% pigeon pea flour, SP1 = 90% sorghum and 10% pigeon pea flour, SP2 = 80% sorghum flour and 20% pigeon pea flour, SP3 = 70% sorghum flour and 30% pigeon pea flour, SP4 = 60% sorghum flour and 40% pigeon pea flour and SP5 = 50% sorghum flour and 50% pigeon pea flour.

The results of this study clearly showed that gruels made from blends of sorghum and pigeon pea flours have improved nutritional value and are more acceptable to the panelists. Therefore, intake of this product by children will help to ameliorate protein malnutrition. Furthermore, use of the underutilized legume, pigeon pea, in the preparation of this product will lead to its increased utilization and value addition.

This study is limited in the determination of the storability of the composite flour blends. Another limitation of the study is the tedious process involved in dehulling of pigeon pea seeds for flour production. It is recommended that families should be educated on the importance of using nutritious gruels from sorghum and pigeon pea flour blends in weaning their children. Further studies should be carried out on shelf stability of the composite flour blends.

4. Conclusion

Composite flours made from mixtures of sorghum and pigeon peas had better approximate composition and functional properties according to this study. With a higher percentage of pigeon pea flour in the blends, there were increases in protein, fiber, and ash and decreases in fat and carbohydrates. The mixtures were also within the recommended dietary intake range for newborns. Compound flours can be used to make baked goods, morning porridge, weaning meals, and other protein-rich foods based on functional properties such as bulk density, water absorbency, oil absorbency, wettability, gelling ability, and swelling index. The sensory qualities of the blends showed that acceptable porridges can be prepared with up to 30% pigeon pea flour and that the blends can be effective in alleviating protein malnutrition in children in Nigeria and other poor countries. Further research should be carried out on ways to optimize the production process.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors proclaim no conflict of attention.

Author Contributions

Dorothy C. Arukwe designed the work, wrote and edited the article. Blessing I. Offia Olua proofread the article while Ebenezer A. Ike collected samples used for the research. All the authors participated in carrying out analysis of the samples. All authors approved the final draft for publication.

Data Availability Statement

Original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the appropriate author.

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